

*Xing zi ming chu 性自命出, Natural Dispositions Come from Endowment

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Entry tags: Guodian Strips, Early Chinese Traditions, Religious Group, Early Chinese text, Excavated text, Text, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

Xing zi ming chu 性自命出, or Natural Dispositions come from Endowment, is a most-debated bamboo manuscript from the Guodian 郭店 corpus, named after the village where the tomb that contained this material was located (modern Hubei, China). The tomb was scientifically excavated in 1993 after being looted, and is dated to the beginning of the third century BCE. The corpus includes manuscripts of the Laozi 老子 (or Dao de jing 道德經), the Ziyi 緇衣 (now a chapter in the Liji 禮記), and other previously unattested texts. All these manuscripts are written in Chu 楚 script and predate the standardization of the script that took place during the Qin 秦 dynasty (221-202 BCE), thus constituting vital evidence for the study of Old Chinese language (scripts and reconstructions). _____ After the publication of the Guodian corpus in 1998, Xing zi ming chu immediately attracted worldwide scholarly attention for its content. According to this manuscript, xing 性 (generally translated as "human nature") can be described as a set of natural dispositions shared by all members of the same species. Xing zi ming chu further details the origin of qing 情 ("emotions"), and how human nature and emotions respond to forms of stimulation such as music (le 樂), rituals (li 禮), and externalities (wu 物). These were all subjects of animated debates during the Warring States era (475-221 BCE); there are in fact several intertextual parallels that can be highlighted between Xing zi ming chu and other texts related to the period. Differently from other discussions of human nature that emerged during the Warring States, Xing zi ming chu is not a treatise with one or more arguments. Rather, it collects statements concerning the topics just listed, with several echoes of other discussions of human nature now part of the body of transmitted literature (such as Mengzi 孟子, Xunzi 荀子, Zhuangzi 莊子, Lushi chunqiu 呂氏春秋). _____ A second wave of enthusiasm for this text took place shortly after 2001, when a group of bamboo manuscripts that appeared on the Hong Kong market in 1994 and were purchased by the Shanghai Museum began to be published. Among these, a manuscript titled by the editors Xing qing lun 性情論 (Discussions on Natural Dispositions and Emotions) parallels some of the content of Xing zi ming chu. The texts have been generally ascribed as close to the Confucian or Ru 儒 tradition, although uncertainties remain concerning their exact positions within intellectual lineages, if any. _____ The manuscripts has been addressed variously: as one coherent unit, as two texts (pian 篇) addressing the same topics, or explored in sections, especially those that resonate most with texts from the body of transmitted literature. In spite of almost twenty years of scholarship on it and the recovery of the Xing qing lun, there are many residual uncertainties about this text, in particular the interpretation of graphs. This poses many questions concerning the nature of this manuscript, who produced it and for what purpose. Unfortunately, being the tomb looted before archeologists could get to it, much of its material artifacts that may have provided useful information was taken. Motivations behind the burial of texts in tombs also remain subject to debate. While the impressive amount of manuscripts from the Warring States period being recovered moved the conversations onto these new collections, the Guodian corpus remains a principal body of material for the understanding of manuscript culture in ancient China, one to which scholars will return to continuously.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 200 BCE

Region: Early and early imperial China

Region tags: Asia, China, East Asia

Core area of early and early imperial China

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Jingmen shi bo wu guan 荆门市博物馆, ed. Guodian Chu Mu Zhujian 郭店楚墓竹简. Di 1 ban. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe 文物出版社, 1998. First publication.

– Source 2: Chen Linqing 陳霖慶. “Xing Qing Lun’ Yi Shi 〈性情論〉譯釋 (Interpretation and Annotations to ‘Discussion on Natural Dispositions and Emotions.’” In Shanghai Bowuguan Cang Zhanguo Chuzhu Shu (Yi) Duben 上海博物館藏戰國楚竹書 (一) 》讀本, 152–221. Taipei Shi: Wan juan lou tu shu you xian gong si, 2004. Best edition to date

– Source 3: Tomohisa Ikeda 池田知久. Kakuten Sokan Jukyō Kenkyū 郭店楚簡儒教研究 (A Study of Confucian Teachings of the Chu Strips of Guodian). Tokyo: Kyuko-Shoin Company 汲古書院, 2003.

Reference: Ding 丁, Yuanzhi 原植. Chu Jian Rujia Xing Qing Shuo Yanjiu 楚簡儒家性情說研究. Taipei Shi: Wanjuanlou tushu youxian gongsi, 2002.

Reference: Middendorf, Ulrike. “Again on ‘qing’. With a Translation of the Guodian ‘xing Zi Ming Chu’”. *Oriens Extremus*, no. 47 (January 1, 2008): 97–159.

Reference: 劉釗, Chen Jian. Guodian Chu Jian Jiaoshi 郭店楚簡校釋. Fujian Renmin Chubanshe 福建人民出版社, 2003.

Reference: Cook, Scott Bradley. “Xing Zi Ming Chu”. In *The Bamboo Texts of Guodian: A Study and Complete Translation*, 667–750. Ithaca, NY: East Asia Program, Cornell University, 2012.

Reference: Lin 林, Zhipeng 志鵬. “郭店竹書《性自命出》上篇約注”. *經學文獻研究集刊*(第18輯). Shanghai: Shanghai Shuju, January 1, 2017, 238–52.

Reference: Puett, Michael. “The Ethics of Responding Properly: The Notion of Qing in Early Chinese Thought”. In *Love and Emotions in Traditional Chinese Literature*, 37–68. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2004.

Reference: Feng 馮, Shengjun 勝君. Guodian Jian Yu Shangbo Jian Duibi Yanjiu 郭店簡與上博簡對比研究. Beijing: Xian zhuang shu ju, 2007.

Reference: Andreini, Attilio. “The Meaning of Qing in Texts from Guodian Tomb No. 1”. In *Love, Hatred, and Other Passions. Questions and Themes on Emotions in Chinese Civilization*, 149–65. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2006.

Reference: Chen 陳, Wei 偉. Guodian Zhushu Bieshi 郭店竹書別釋. Wuhan: Hubeijiaoyu, 2003.

Reference: Poli, Maddalena. “Graphs and Words. Interpreting 取 in Xing Zi Ming Chu 性自命出”, no. 2 (2021).

Reference: Slingerland, Edward. "The Problem of Moral Spontaneity in the Guodian Corpus". *Dao* 7 (2008): 237–56.

Reference: Cheng 程, Hao 浩. "清华简《四告》的性质与结构". *Chutu Wenxian 出土文献* 3 (January 1, 2020): 21–36.

Reference: Cook, Scott Bradley. *The Bamboo Texts of Guodian: A Study and Complete Translation*. Vol. 2. Ithaca, NY: East Asia Program, Cornell University, 2012.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: CText 中國哲學書電子化計劃 <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&chapter=438279> (not updated with the most recent studies)

– Source 1 Description: Wikisource <https://zh.wikisource.org/wiki/郭店楚墓竹簡#性命自出> (not update with the most recent studies)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: Wikisource <https://zh.wikisource.org/wiki/郭店楚墓竹簡>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Notes: Xing zi ming chu runs on 67 strips, most of which intact and well preserved. Xing qing lun is a manuscripts in 40 strips, may of which poorly preserved.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field does not know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The Xing zi ming chu is currently stored in the Hubei Provincial Museum 湖北省博物馆; the Xing qing lun is in the Shanghai Museum 上海博物館. Neither manuscript is on display, due to preservation reasons.

Reference: Hubei Museum. "Images of the Guodian Manuscripts from the Hubei Museum Website". Hubei Museum, n.d.. <http://www.hbww.org/Views/Collection.aspx?PNo=Collection&No=ZJ&type=List>.

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: Note that the tomb was robbed before archeologists could excavated is scientifically.

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– *Specify*: The Guodian tomb is located modern Hubei. When the archeologists reached it, it had already been looted, but the looters left behind the manuscripts (this was either due to disattention or unawareness of how remunerative these would be). The textual parallel Xing qing lun instead was not scientifically excavated.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Potentially, anyone with adequate literacy level.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Xing zi ming chu and Xing qing lun are often considered as two versions of the same text. The two however texts vary considerably in the second half, in that both texts present sentences that are not found in the other. Other differences include graphic variants (two different graphs used to write the same word) and morphological variants (two different graphs write two different words).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

Notes: No manuscript is seen as more proper since too little is known about these otherwise unattested texts.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Xing zi ming chu is part of the Guodian corpus of manuscript; these were all found in the same tomb. Yet, it does not directly follow that this collection circulated as such before being buried. The Xing qing lun is part of the collection now known as Shanghai Museum (which acquired such material). Being looted, we will never know if all the texts that now form the Shanghai corpus were found together.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Xing zi Ming Chu is often considered a text belonging to the so-called Confucian (Ru 儒) tradition, although some scholars also believe it contains ideas close to texts eventually labelled as

Daoist.

Reference: Slingerland, Edward. "The Problem of Moral Spontaneity in the Guodian Corpus". *Dao* 7 (2008): 237-56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11712-008-9066-9>.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Xing zi ming chu lacks any sustained argument; it represents a series of statements concerning the topics introduced above. Furthermore, it includes paragraphs that are composed by a list of definitions; others resemble a collection of statements which could have circulated independently. I suspect this text represents attempts at defining the philosophical scope of human nature, and how to discuss it.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Although the text has been identified by many scholars as belonging to the Confucian (Ru) 儒 tradition.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to xin 心, a term that indicates both the emotional ("heart") and cognitive faculties ("mind") of a person. For example, it talks of the effects of teaching on the mind.

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: There is no explicit indication of anything like a "soul" in the Xing zi ming chu, nor that the heart-mind continues to live after death.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: Heaven (tian 天) is mentioned only once as source of endowment (ming 命), from which human nature derives. There is however no indication of Heaven as a supernatural being. The sentence (性自命出，命自天降。) is concerned with establishing an order, in my view.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Xing Zi Ming Chu closes with a definition of the moral person (junzi 君子), but much of its wording is still subject of debate, making it hard to understand exactly what is meant (君子執志必有夫光光之心，出言必有夫栗栗之信，賓客之禮必有夫齊齊之容，祭祀之禮必有夫齊齊之敬，居喪必有夫戀戀之哀。君子身以為主心。). Other virtues are discussed below.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: The text discusses benevolence (ren 仁) as one of the directions (assuming this is what fang 方 means) of human nature, 仁，性之方也。It further states that of the seven kinds of love, benevolence is the one closest to human nature, 愛類七，唯性愛為近仁。No identification of the "seven kinds of love" has been reached yet.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: Morality (yi 義) is addressed variously in the text. For example, it is said to be the orientation (if fang 方 is so understood) of respect, 義，敬之方也, and to sharpen human nature. Yi 義 is also used to indicate what is proper.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The Xing Zi Ming Chu was produced around 300 BCE, during the Warring States era. During this period, The Zhou 周 court loses its monopoly on political control and cultural production. Each state becomes more and more centralized, and society is more militarized (being the states continuously at war, as the name of this historical moment suggests). Each state competes for territorial and cultural monopoly, likely one of the reasons behind the abundance production and variety of written sources at this stage.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None that the field knows about.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: It likely circulated in educational settings, about which we know too little to determine the level of formality.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Except that, because of social practices, education remained for centuries primarily a male institution.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: The text is concerned only with statements and reflections on human nature, emotions, music, and virtues (see introduction).

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: The text is concerned only with statements and reflections on human nature, emotions, music, virtues, and how the mind is stimulated. No mention to public works is done.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: The text is concerned only with statements and reflections on human nature, emotions, music, and virtues (see introduction).

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: The text is concerned only with statements and reflections on human nature, emotions, music, and virtues (see introduction).

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text is concerned only with statements and reflections on human nature, emotions, music, and virtues (see introduction).

Bibliography

General References

Reference: *Xing zi ming chu 性自命出, Natural Dispositions Come from Endowment, Perkins, Franklin. "Motivation and the Heart in the Xing Zi Ming Chu". *Dao* 8 (2009): 117–81.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Jingmen shi bo wu guan 荆门市博物馆, ed. Guodian Chu Mu Zhujian 郭店楚墓竹简. Di 1 ban. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe 文物出版社, 1998. First publication., Source 2: Chen Linqing 陳霖慶. "Xing Qing Lun' Yi Shi 〈性情論〉譯釋 (Interpretation and Annotations to 'Discussion on Natural Dispositions and Emotions.'" In Shanghai Bowuguan Cang Zhanguo Chuzhu Shu (Yi) Duben 上海博物館藏戰國楚竹書 (一) 讀本, 152–221. Taipei Shi: Wan juan lou tu shu you xian gong si, 2004. Best edition to date, Source 3: Tomohisa Ikeda 池田知久. Kakuten Sokan Jukyō Kenkyū 郭店楚簡儒教研究 (A Study of Confucian Teachings of the Chu Strips of Guodian). Tokyo: Kyuko-Shoin Company 汲古書院, 2003., Ding 丁, Yuanzhi 原植. Chu Jian Rujia Xing Qing Shuo Yanjiu 楚簡儒家性情說研究. Taipei Shi: Wanjuanlou tushu youxian gongsi, 2002.

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